

1 **Senescence during lineage commitment in the human embryo.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here identification of
9 components of the senescence program including IL-32 and MDK as lineage commitment factor or lineage
10 commitment cooperating factor in embryonic stem cells of the human embryo.

11 Citations

- 12 1. Deryabin, P.I., Ivanova, J.S. and Borodkina, A.V., 2021. Senescence of stromal cells contributes to
13 endometrium dysfunction and embryo implantation failure. bioRxiv, pp.2021-07.
- 14 2. Singh, V.P., McKinney, S. and Gerton, J.L., 2020. Persistent DNA damage and senescence in the
15 placenta impacts developmental outcomes of embryos. Developmental cell, 54(3), pp.333-347.
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